

CERTIFICACIÓN DE TRADUCCIÓN

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CERTIFICO

Que he realizado la traducción del proyecto de integración curricular titulado "**AJUSTE DE LA ARQUITECTURA MOBILENETV3 PARA LA IDENTIFICACIÓN DE MADERA CON UN CONJUNTO DE DATOS PERSONALIZADO**" del idioma español al idioma inglés, presentada por **JORGE DANIEL ORTEGA ALBURQUEQUE**, portador de la cédula de identidad: **3050093776**, como requisito para obtener el título de ingeniero en ciencias de la computación en la Universidad Nacional de Loja.

Por medio de este certificado, aseguro que la traducción del proyecto ha sido realizada de acuerdo con los estándares y prácticas de traducción vigentes, y que el resultado final es una versión precisa y comprensible del documento original.

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Abstract

Illegal logging and deforestation represent critical threats to the sustainability of forest ecosystems in southern Ecuador, highlighting the urgent need for efficient and accessible in situ control tools. This study aimed to develop and evaluate the performance of a lightweight artificial intelligence model for the automated identification of timber species. An experimental methodology was applied using the MobileNetV3 Large lightweight architecture as the base model. Four experiments were conducted by alternating the use of Transfer Learning and the Triple Attention mechanism to enhance the extraction of anatomical features. A custom dataset of 3,600 macroscopic images was used, covering four ecologically important species: cedar (*Meliaceae Cedrela* sp.), walnut (*Juglandaceae Juglans neotropica*), faique (*Fabaceae Vachellia macracantha*), and guayacán (*Bignoniaceae Handroanthus chrysanthus*). The results showed, both in the main performance metrics and in the ablation study, that the integration of Triple Attention led to unstable and inferior predictions compared to fine-tuning the base model using data augmentation. The latter approach achieved a test accuracy of 84.0%, with accuracy and F1-score values of 81.6% and 81.8%, respectively. It was concluded that the proposed model offers a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency, with potential for future improvement. Thus, it represents a robust and viable technological solution for potential implementation in portable tools supporting forest monitoring and as a didactic resource.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, illegal logging, forest monitoring, species identification, lightweight models.